

YouCount
Youth Citizen Science

D6.5

Final report on ethical issues encountered during the YouCount project

Raminta Pučėtaitė¹, Reidun Norvoll²,

- 1 Kaunas University of Technology, Kaunas, Lithuania
- 2 Work Research Institute, OsloMet, Oslo, Norway

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D6.5 Final report on the ethical issues encountered during the project

This deliverable summarizes the main ethical issues faced by the project partner teams when implementing the project and how these have been considered, mitigated and handled. It aims to share the experience with other researchers in Citizen Social Science (CSS) and raise the questions to the attention of the European Commission (EC) to facilitate further developments of Citizen Science (CS) as an integral part of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and Open Science (OS).

Table 1: Revision history

VERSION	DATE	CREATED BY	COMMENTS
1.0	12/ 12 / 2023	Partner No. 1 – OsloMet/ Partner No. 7 – KTU	Structure and content
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1.2	30/01/2024	Partner No. 7 - KTU	Revisions
1.3	31/ 01 / 2024	P1, Reidun Norvoll	Final version submitted

Table 2: Terms and Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	FULL TERM
AB	Advisory Board
CS	Citizen Science
CSS	Citizen Social Science
D	Deliverable

DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
LL	Living Labs
OS	Open Science
PAR	Participatory Action Research
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SEB	Safety and Ethics Board
Y-CSS	Youth Citizen Social Science
YCS	Young Citizen Scientist
YouCount App	'YouCount CSS app' on the SPOTTERON CS platform
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The deliverable at hand outlines the key tensions that the YouCount Consortium faced during the project period lasting for three years. It lists ethical principles which were considered at the beginning of the project anticipating certain challenges and/or ethical risks when conducting citizen social science with young people and sheds empirical light on the ways of mitigating those which realised. These are mostly related to recruiting and motivating youth citizen social scientists (YCS), GDPR and Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) to professional researchers, and the relational aspects of conducting citizen social science in national cases focusing on different youth groups with the risk of vulnerability with different social targets to ensure social inclusion. Based on these reflected experiences recommendations to the citizen science community and the EC to ensure the balance of procedural ethics and discretion of researchers as well as epistemology of Open Science are formulated.

1. Introduction: anticipating ethical issues in citizen science

The deliverable at hand reflects experiences of applying ethical principles to the praxis of citizen social science. This reflection has been informed by the key principles of ethical research, including respect for research participants and informed consent (Vanclay et al., 2013) which secure autonomy, dignity, non-maleficence and beneficence, justice, and ethics of care to research participants (Koepsell, 2017). Moreover, the research was generally guided by the RRI principles of anticipation, inclusion, reflexivity, responsiveness, and stakeholder engagement (Lubberink et al., 2017; Stilgoe et al., 2013) and the recommended standards for CS research with vulnerable participants such as youth, i.e., inclusivity, adaptability, sensitivity, safety, and reciprocity (Chesser et al., 2020; see more in Butkevičienė et al., 2021).

The deliverable draws on the other deliverables of the YouCount project covering ethical principles in citizen science research, from recruiting YCS (Pučėtaitė and Norvoll, 2021; Butkevičienė et al., 2021) through data collection (Ridley and Norvoll, 2022), personal data protection (Norvoll and Pučėtaitė, 2021) to meta analysis of cross-case experiences (Ridley et al., 2023) and meta-analysis of the project outcomes (Saumer et al., 2023), D5.3 Handbook and toolkit (Borgströmet al., 2024) for youth citizen social science. It also builds on the discussion initiated by the project researchers Canto-Farachala et al. (2023) on participatory communication via CSS and Mihók et al. (2023) on slow science and relational ethics. It shares lessons learnt from balancing the principles of including socially marginalized social groups that were meant to be empowered through CSS activities and avoiding any harm to them as obliged by legal provisions of personal data protection and data management set by the GDPR and national Civil Law of the partner countries as well as the ethics of care in leaving the research field and the participating youths.

1.1 Participants and data

The project rests on Participatory Action Research (PAR) as the epistemic foundation of citizen social sciences (Albert et al., 2021) and the Participatory Communication approach that is a legacy of Paulo Freire's notions of dialogic communication and praxis (Freire, 1996; also see Canto-Farachala et al., 2023). This approach highlights the uniqueness of each community when searching solutions to their problems with researchers, arguing that while development processes may have universal characteristics, the solutions would always be local (Rifkin, 1996).

The project included young people from a wide age range from 13 to 30 years old in the role of both research participants and co-researchers in the research teams. The project focused on youths in general but addressed the circumstances of youths who are most at risk of exclusion in terms of

e.g., poverty, migration, disability and unemployment, or living in disadvantaged urban/rural areas and thus meet the criteria for vulnerability beside being adolescents or minors (Pučėtaitė and Norvoll, 2021). When YCS under 18 years were involved, according to the national laws, informed consents were sought not only from them but also from their parents or guardians and ethical approvals were obtained by each partner.

The activities carried out by national project teams in developing case studies used a dialogical style to foster a climate of mutual respect, acknowledgement of sometimes painful life experiences for the participating YCS. This dialogical approach was particularly seen as a means to build relationships of trust and take into consideration the ethical principles of non-maleficence and ethics of care. YCS also provided inputs to their perspective on social inclusion and targeted solutions through participating in local dialogue forums (e.g., group conversations or ‘listenings’). Each case established local living labs (LLs) with multiple stakeholders in the wider community or targeted stakeholder organisations, which used the data provided by the participating YCS to cocreate policy-making and innovations in terms of new ideas, products or methods as a way to create social change as a dimension of social innovation (Pataki et al., 2023).

Depending on the national case, young citizen scientists in the YouCount project were involved in the design and use of qualitative and quantitative methods and developed methods for sharing and communicating the project with local stakeholders. Co-creation activities were covered by the ethical approvals and informed consents were gained from the participants of dialogical forums and LLs. To avoid any social or emotional harm to YCS and prevent overburdening them with increasing workload that could not be anticipated, the project made use of the Safety and Ethics Board (SEB) who advised the Consortium on any potential risks arising to YCS.

YCS were also involved in the development, pilot, use and evaluation of an application for smartphones and computer named the YouCount App Toolkit (hereinafter, the YouCount App). The experience with ethical and data protection improvement was among one of the key challenges during the implementation of Y-CSS, for example as described by Canto-Farachala et al. (2023) and in the Project Handbook (Borgstöm et al., 2024). As the project strived for empowering youth and rested on the assumption of adolescents’ maturity to voice their concerns in relation to social inclusion, the practices related to GDPR requirements in relation to DPIA was experienced by the YouCount coordinator and case researchers as an important barrier or tension to the principle of inclusivity (see section 2.2 for more detail).

Overall, the data collected during the project include:

- Textual data: recordings, minutes, summaries from dialogue forums/interviews and case work, transcripts, field notes or comments provided by YCS on the YouCount App.
- Tabular data: aggregated and anonymised data based on quantitative data collection undertaken in WP 2, 3 & 4 by use of questionnaires and YouCount App.

- Image data: Image files for research illustration and in user generated data and recordings.
- Audio data: Mainly records in the sound recorder/dictaphone during interviews, which were deleted after transcribing and anonymising the data.
- Other: Interactive data (between YCS) on the YouCount App, online-forum for YCS across countries and presentation of stakeholder organisations on the project webpage.

1.2 Key discussion points about ethical issues in CS

Beside procedural ethics that is important for ensuring dignity, autonomy, beneficence and non-maleficence and justice to research participants there are also ethical implications to CSS stemming from the ethics of care. These included for example issues concerning how the relationships with youth groups were built and how the research field was left preventing any social or/and emotional harm to individuals who acted in double roles of research participants and research team members. As indicated by Canto-Farachala et al. (2023) and Borgström et al. (2024), research ethics and relational ethics are integral part of participatory research and CSS in particular. Relational ethics is particularly relevant for young co-researchers deeply involved in the research teams and who had an active role in them for a long time. The research teams perceived that it is important to take good care of them and avoid overburdening them in line with the ethical principles of respect and justice.

In addition, vulnerability of YCS in the YouCount project presupposed following the obligation for professional researchers not only to rely on the principles of reciprocity and inclusivity, which implies questioning data protection requirements from the ethical perspective as being over-protective or paternalistic, but also consider the principles of adaptability, sensitivity, and safety. In CSS practice, they translate to the need to present the information about the research beyond a textual form, e.g., in pictures or audio records if YCS are illiterate, cannot read in a particular (foreign to them) language or because their vision is impaired, and explain potential risks in the language that they understand. Realizing the justice principle demands from professional researchers to give credit to YCS who have made substantial contribution to the research either via acknowledgement in the publication or co-authorship (Rasmussen, 2019). The principle of justice is in particular outspoken in CSS as individuals are engaging in research activities voluntarily. Using monetary “rewards” to increase the motivation and engagement of YCS in the YouCount project was not allowed by the EU. It was a tension lived through by experienced PAR researchers who felt moral obligation to compensate the YCS to avoid exploitation and increase their engagement. Therefore, each national team addressed this ethical principle, and the solutions were solved through accepted national and university regulations and procedures in their country according to alternative eligible possibilities.

Finally, the Consortium anticipated some social and psychological risks that would undermine the ethical principle of non-maleficence. Use of the YouCount App and participation in the LL could

expose YCS and other participants who do not belong to the vulnerable groups to negative feedback. Mitigation of this risk involved by the YouCount App coordinators as well as moderators of the dialogical activities. The App management team were monitoring the information on the YouCount App to prevent violations; the app also included possibilities for blocking or reporting users. YCS were encouraged by professional researchers to inform them as soon as something happened and not to carry this on their own (e.g., feeling personal shame). Moreover, although the research focus was on youths' positive experiences with social participation, discussions and reflections concerning social inclusion were anticipated to possibly stir negative feelings and memories of situations where they (in particular, refugees) had felt excluded/marginalised. Discussing negative experiences and difficulties openly can be both healing and burdening. Consequently, the researchers and collaborating communities/organisations were cautious about how the YCS felt about participation, not only as they expressed in verbally but also through their body language during the research activities to make sure they participated voluntarily and to offer any necessary support and guidance if they seemed unsafe.

The Consortium anticipated that some challenges may arise when gaining ethical approvals for the research part involving mobile device for data collection, such as the YouCount App (Butkevičienė et al., 2021). As noted by Rasmussen (2019), ethical commissions often treat these data as personal data. As the YouCount App collected the geolocation data and metadata of the research participants through pictures, this was considered as risk to vulnerable research participants (YCS), and their communities. Based on these GDPR risks, "Sikt" (previously Norwegian Centre for Research Data) required a Data Protection Impact Assessment (hereafter DPIA) after the piloting of the app and just before launching the app study for a larger population of YCS in the local cases. The YouCount App was designed in the way that it does not collect any technical nor personal data via cookies. It was foreseen that when registering the research participants will be advised to use nicknames and avatars instead of real names and photographs to avoid any personal data disclosure. Contact information such as email address had an option to be marked as public or private. Data processing procedures were included in a joint responsibility agreement for data processing for case partners and additional data processing agreement between OsloMet as coordinator with SPOTTERON on behalf of the consortium. Each national team had designated 1-2 team members responsible for data processing, while just two Consortium members had access to the registration data of the YouCount App users. Only processed data was to be transferred between the partners in an anonymous or deidentified way (e.g., ID- number/pseudonym).

Finally, an ethical issue that is highlighted in prior CS research relates to research data and output quality. Citizen scientists, in contrast to professional ones, are not governed nor monitored by, e.g. research institutions nor are they accountable to public funding bodies for research quality or producing certain output promised in the research proposal. The Consortium anticipated this risk and reflected on the practices for quality assurance together with the SEB and Advisory Board (AB). Agreement between the partners existed that training of YCS must take place before research and

innovation activities. Sections of training are outlined in D1.2 (Butkevičienė et al., 2021) and D5.3 Handbook and toolkit (Borgström et al, 2024).

The following part of the deliverable reports on lessons learnt from applying research and relational ethics in the practice of CSS.

2. *YouCount navigating ethical challenges*

2.1 *Recruitment and motivation of youth considered vulnerable*

Following the Grant Agreement (GA) with the EC and D6.6 Recruitment and consent procedures, the project team implemented informed consent procedures to ensure voluntary participation. Ethical approvals were gained by each partner institution for case studies (Ridley and Norvoll, 2023). YCS recruitment channels ranged from contacting non-governmental organizations working with refugees to formal school environments, depending on the social problem tackled by the national partner. In all national cases, professional researchers' teams considered respect for YCS privacy, voluntariness (lack of pressure or undue influence to participate), accurate and clear (unbiased) description of the study and avoiding misconception of the outcomes of participation or research results.

Motivation of the youth to get involved in the research project on long-term basis varied across the countries, partly depending on the approaches the national research teams used to engage them. For ethics purposes, the project partners tried to recruit a balanced number between genders, although the 50-50 balance was not reached in most of the national cases.

In some national cases such as Austria (Ridley et al., 2023), YCS were engaged in the role of a researcher already at the initial phase when based on the professional researchers' guidance they co-created a visually and textually appealing informed consent rather than using standard institutional forms, although stylistically adopted to youth and their parents/guardians. At the same time, this activity served as an awareness raising tool on the process of social science research as well as the legal and ethical principles that have to be followed by researchers. Employing "mock-MAXQDA" workshop, which is also a more general tool as a new language to (more engaging) science literacy and education activities (<https://www.fedora-project.eu/new-languages>), also contributed as a tool for learning the data analysis process with software that integratively contributed to quality assurance of reliability of the findings. Monitoring the progress of the research on posters reminding a canvas tool used for the SCRUM methodology in project management in the Danish case (Ridley et al., 2023) also added to building an environment of mutual respect and sharing as activities of the research project gained more transparency, which was driving YCS engagement in the project. Prior cooperation with the school in the Danish case

worked to the advantage while in the Lithuanian case researchers were in contact with Panevėžys district schools for the first time and it took much longer to start a dialogical activity and gain trust. YCS' voluntariness to participate and stay engaged in the YouCount activities were much higher in the former rather than the latter case. Also, gaining support from policy-makers in the LL activities as demonstrated by the Austrian case contributed to reducing the drop-out rate and fostering youth engagement in CSS as they experienced the moment of being heard and acknowledged, which aligns with the ethical principle of securing YCS as research participants' dignity.

To some extent, following formal consent procedures and getting informed consent signed when recruiting and involving YCS into the project was affecting professional researchers' teams rather than YCS. For this group, going through a long informed consent letter when registering as the YouCount App as demanded by the DPIA decision played a more significant role in retaining interest and motivation to use the YouCount App (see next section).

2.2 GDPR challenges to inclusive science

Overall, the YouCount project did not use any intrusive methods nor collected sensitive personal information. Still, the objectives of gaining increased knowledge of societal challenges as seen from the citizens' own perspectives, outcome analysis for individual citizen scientists, and analysis of data in regard to specific variables (i.e., cultural background, social status, age and gender), made it necessary to record and work with some personal related information. Potential occurrence of personal and sensitive data was expected through the ongoing conversations during the research process.

The YouCount App included data collection opportunities of relevance for the ethics and policy discussion below: GIS data (place based – interactive map); Quantitative (spots, survey data); Qualitative (commentary text fields); Images (e.g., pictures); Actions (own /others, e.g., participation in activities); and Interactions (e.g., comments/reactions to each other/networking). Participants were informed that their home address should not be spotted. The App differs from ordinary social media platforms by not allowing hidden personal messages or use of negative emojis (only hearts).

The piloting of the YouCount App was approved relatively easily by the supervisory authorities (e.g., ethics committees, data protection authorities) as the use of the qualitative and quantitative methods is common research practice, and the co-design process was not new to them. Yet, when the time came to launch the YouCount App to young people in general, the supervisory authorities (Sikt) in Norway requested a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) according to the General Data Protection Regulation art. 35 no. 1. The request for a DPIA, unveiled the challenges related to open CSS due to its research focus and more personal character (Canto-Farachala et al., 2023). For

instance, the Norwegian supervisory authorities assessed that “the planned processing of personal data will involve a relatively high risk to the rights and freedoms of the data subjects”. The concerns were related to: Processing special categories of personal data (sensitive information), or information of a more personal character; Processing of personal data on a large scale, both in terms of sample size, amount of information (variables), duration and regularity; Combining data sets (e.g., different purposes and/or different data controllers) in a way that exceeds the data subject's reasonable expectations; Processing of personal data about vulnerable individuals, and partly minors.

The DPIA was approved after two months with the following consequences for the project: (i) a long, formal, and extensive written consent form integrated in the YouCount App; (ii), limitation in the use of the YouCount App to local case participants; (iii), a system for parental consent for minors or exclusion of opportunities to participate for those under 16/18 years when parental consent was too difficult to achieve; (iv) extended guidelines to require use of pseudonyms, no identifiable pictures of self or others, and (v) procedures for safe data transfer/storage and use of an App moderator group to prevent possible personal or improper content (already planned for, but more underlined).

While the DPIA to some extent contributed to strengthen data protection considerations and technical/organisations measures to safeguard participants, the consequences described above resulted in the tendency of excluding the youngest participants from the study, and to reduced possibilities for open personal engagement in science through digital tools, compared to CS in natural sciences. Moreover, the GDPR assessment process displayed that several data related to youths' observations of social inclusion opportunities were 'automatically' considered as sensitive data (for example, spots or comments related to religious meeting places as important for social belonging). Social data was thus often regarded as more personal and riskier, especially the open commentary fields in the app and the interactive functions. The need for control and disclosure curtailed its use for open dialogical communication. The innovative purposes of the project were also regarded as out of the scope for the formal assessments, keeping a strict distinction between research and innovation, which conflicts with EU science policy and the GA for the YouCount project.

Another tension was between the ideal of citizen- generated data in CSS and the project's focus on young citizen scientists as equal partners or contributions/active agents in co- creative processes versus the traditional focus on participants as 'objects for science' and request for high research control of the data from the researchers. More overarching policy and ethical considerations concerning the underlining understanding of youth, sensitive data or vulnerability as more nuanced individual traits or power relations, were regarded as outside the scope for the DPIA assessment because the university contract with the supervisory authorities only included legal data protection issues and not ethical considerations. This institutional separation of data protection and ethics approval assessments, especially related to CSS (as social sciences and not health research) hampered the possibility of finding a good balance between the needs for disclosure and risk

mitigation strategies with current policy aiming to provide youth and marginalised citizens to have a say in policy and science.

The challenges of more nuanced considerations of responsible citizen engagement were also enforced by a tendency to “automatically” frame youths as ‘children’ (and not adolescents) or as ‘vulnerable’ instead of being adult participants. While the researchers found the written consent letter as too long and bureaucratic for the participating youth groups, this could not be changed as they required some standard formalities concerning GDPR. Broader and common ethics concerns and considerations were thus disconnected from GDPR, and the ethical epistemology of inclusive science and participatory communication behind GDPR legislation was left out. This GDPR logic also seemed to reinforce a paternalistic ethics where the user- involvement perspectives were downplayed to a larger extent than before, at least in a Norwegian setting. The many different and multi-level actors following the new GDPR in combination with the novelty of the YouCount App tool, also complicated the process, increased workload and delayed the processes which reduced the possibilities of using the YouCount App during the implementation period also in terms of planned app-event weeks. Some national research teams experienced drop out of the already engaged YCS as activities related to the YouCount App use were deterred, which was important for the teams where fragile new relationships were established.

It is also worth mentioning that the potential risks were not realised other than a need for a few corrections of the use of recognisable pictures (with no sensitive information) or self-chosen personal name as a user profile. In general, the youths adhered well to the guidelines and breach of guidelines where much more innocent compared to common social media channels for youths. The integrated data protection functionalities in the SPOTTERON app solution, organisational measures (such as supervision and data transfer procedures) as well as lack of possibilities of hidden personal or negative messages may have been good protective measures. The overall experience is, however, that the anticipated challenges or risks when engaging youth in this kind of adjusted social media activities was greater than the actual harm. Creating engagement for participation was a greater challenge. To what extent the risks of harm and break of GDPR would have been greater with a more openly launched CSS app study is unknown but could be tried out in later studies as the collected data seemed to have some promising aspects for knowledge generation and increased social science engagement for some youths (D2.3, Ridley et al., 2023).

2.3 Applying ethics of care in the research process

Ethics of care, which is a relational moral theory, holds that any human being is capable of raising care and concern for others as relations are fundamental to humans as social beings (Gilligan, 1982). It is an alternative and legitimate criterion to justice as an ethical principle. Ethics of care distinguishes between two different aspects of care, i.e., caring for as “actual hands-on application

of caring services” and caring about as “a state of being whereby one nurtures caring ideas or intentions” (Sander-Staudt, 2019). Hence, caring is contextual, responsive to particular needs of definite others. At the heart of caring is empathy. Empathy is combined from a number of psychological capacities, which enables humans “to know what other people are thinking and feeling, to emotionally engage with them, to share their thoughts and feelings, and to care for their well-being” (Stueber, 2019). Hence, ethics of care postulates the normativity of interpersonal care, in particular, if a relationship of dependence is present. This does not mean that care is paternalistic and makes someone less efficacious, self-dependent etc. Proper caring develops the others as personalities with their authenticity and identity by responding to their needs, values, expectations and well-being. In other words, care ethics and empathy, if properly practiced, help the other to grow.

Ethics of care is very relevant to CSS targeting social impact such as social inclusion and transformation of lives of a definite social group. As YouCount’s focus is also on youth as a vulnerable group, ethics of care is particularly relevant in the research conduct and closing the project activities. Below the experiences of the project partners in this respect are reflected. More specifically, we wished to highlight two aspects related to ethics in CSS research: (i) tensions experienced by professional researchers because generating change such as social inclusion takes time and emotional resources, which leaves fewer resources for, e.g. publishing the results of these processes, which is essential for academic career and to meet the commitments to the funding organization; (ii) leaving the research scene once relationships of trust have been created and ensuring the capacity of the YCS to live self-dependent life in their communities.

2.3.1 Targeting transformations and monitoring the publication track

As discussed in the research and ethics literature, good conduct of research is not only related to formal ethical procedures but should be included in the researcher’s demeanour and social interactions with the field/participants throughout the whole research process and sensitiveness to the participants’ needs and concerns. This particularly applies to fieldwork when the researchers engage more directly with the field and for a longer period of time. Work with vulnerable groups may be paradoxical in that sense that it is both challenging and rewarding. It is challenging as at first the target groups meet professional researchers with distrust a priori because of their social Otherness (e.g., for refugee youth), demonstrate no willingness to participate in an international study because of the language or understanding social science as irrelevant in their social environment or because of their disability may require extra efforts and emotional resources. It is rewarding because when change happens and people become more connected, socially integrated, find jobs, gain citizenship rights etc. professional researchers may experience elevation of doing meaningful work and serving the society, which is important for people with high level of public service motivation (which many researchers have).

The ups and downs of such a research process with dialogical activities and co-created social change takes time and therefore it is 'slow science' (Mihók et al., 2023). For example, in addition to developing friendly relationships the researchers may have to think in different terms when considering the space where they meet with YCS. For example, as noted by the project partners who worked with the hard of hearing YCS (Mihók et al., 2023), "As visual communication plays an essential role, organization of space is about creating a visually accessible and safely structured place". Practising ethics of care demanded from professional researchers not only to arrange the space in a way that it eliminates artefacts of power but also to develop "self-awareness in terms of positioning, speech speed, articulation and non-verbal communication" (ibid.). As researchers noted, hearing people may discriminate hard-of-hearing ones by simply having a verbal exchange with the face turned away from them.

Moreover, work with any YCS for the partners was a conscious trust-building process, which took months. The results were more rewarding for the partners who worked with considerably smaller groups in the first meetings. Those who attempted to recruit YCS from large groups (e.g., 30-50 youths) had more challenges in securing interest and positive responses as they did not have enough time for knowing their participants initially. For example, scheduling meetings after school and having limited time until a school bus brings youth from school home does not allow enough time for sharing stories, which is an important aspect in building relationships and which worked to the advantage of the research teams operating in urban environments in close distance between university and the YCS communities. Meeting potential candidates in smaller groups may have yielded a different result but, for example, the choice of rural communities more than 100 km away from the research performing organization did not allow to allocate as much time as needed. Hence, one important lesson learnt in CSS process is giving enough time for collaborative efforts, which also adds to motivation of YCS.

As the research process is time demanding and ethical approvals, in particular for using the YouCount App, also take extra time compared to the 'classical' social science studies, delivering research output may become problematic. First, the evidence for social transformation may show up after the project ends. Some positive outcomes may be reported by the YCS, but the answers may be criticised for social desirability or procedural biases. Hence, in order to deliver on time, preparation before the actual research takes place is essential (Mihók, 2024). Second, the results of transformations may not be interesting enough for the academic community for lack of conceptual rigour. For example, reporting the outputs in YCS joining informal networks or finding jobs as a result of participation in the project does not carry much value academically, yet, these results bear significant social impact. Hence, evaluating effects of a citizen science project in a quantitative manner may not lead to a high-level publication while focusing on qualitative methodologies for reflecting results is a typical choice. However, a high-quality qualitative analysis demands expertise from professional researchers, implying a need for close cooperation between senior and junior researchers, not speaking about inclusion of citizen scientists who are not trained to write academic papers.

2.3.2 Leaving the research scene

Ethics of care demands from professional researchers who initiated participatory communication and collaborative research to consider the ways they leave YCS and their communities. It may be hard for both professional researchers and YCS. Ending the relationship increases the need for awareness that a project is time bound and will end at some point (Byantropologene & OSIRIS, 2023). Exiting collaborative research field and moving from, e.g. regular meetings just to random ones, may be a gradual closing process where both the researchers and participating youths get some time to be prepared for the ending of the project. While young people in risk of social exclusion can be resourceful and fully capable of participating in citizen social science, some may also be in a more exposed or dependent situation due to poverty, lack of formal citizenship, disabilities and more (Norvoll, 2024). It is therefore important to mitigate feelings of being “abandoned” and to consider if the active participation and benefits can be continued in some ways on a local level.

Another obligation stems from research funding with public finance. It obliges the Consortium to consider how social innovation can be made sustainable. A short project perspective needs to be balanced with a longer outlook. In YouCount, many case partners organised some continuous contact or closing events in the last part of the project and after its end, in some cases acknowledging YCS’s participation by diplomas or recommendation letters. In addition, as YouCount was a learning experience not only to YCS but also to professional researchers, discussing the lessons learnt and collecting feedback from the YCS and/or their communities where possible at the end of the project was considered ethically appropriate (Norvoll, 2024).

Securing sustainability of the project for social impact in the YouCount is related to the experience gained by YCS and other stakeholders in the living labs. These dialogical activities will be continued by youth in some national cases. In addition, some of the closing meetings were focusing on creating a long-term impact of the project and discussing how the project work could be taken further locally or on a European level.

3. Recommendations to the CS community and the EC

From what has been said above about the YouCount researchers’ experience of ethics in and of citizen social science, the following recommendations follow **to the CS community**:

- Recruiting CSS works best if trust is present in one way or another: if interpersonal trust between professional researchers and potential citizen scientists did not exist, a school or any organisation that the target audience trusts can facilitate the process of recruiting CSS;
- To maintain motivation of CSS, acknowledgement of voluntary efforts is a must. This may range from recommendation letters to potential employees to diplomas of appreciation.

Arranging the ethics training activities in a way that is appealing to youth (i.e. making it as experiential as possible) can contribute to retaining them in the project;

- A CSS project targeting not only education but also social change demands relationship building, therefore, allocating sufficient time, finding a safe space for meetings and proper scheduling to avoid haste in dialogical activities or fatigue is essential;
- Considerable time to gain ethical approvals from ethics committees must be allocated, and the process of ethical approval must be started early enough. In particular, if the citizen scientists meet any category of vulnerability or personal data may be collected with digital devices. Complexity may increase in international projects as national legislation may have different implications to data protection. Including an IT specialist into the research where an App is used may be beneficial to gain ethical approval;
- A plan how to capitalise on the results of a time-bound, comparatively short-term project to long-term social impact helps to realise the researcher's (or research performing organization's) responsibility to a funding organization.

Our recommendations for **the EC** as the funding organization relate to:

- Time framing of citizen science, in particular citizen social science, projects: a longer time period for the projects with CSS epistemology must be allocated as relationship building for social or political transformations, gaining ethical approvals is time-taking;
- Research output from CSS must also embrace the so-called grey-literature if the ethical imperative to acknowledge citizen scientists as co-researchers and co-authors is kept;
- Giving voice to youth (e.g. adolescents) via technologies such as Apps does not necessarily put them at higher risk than other social groups. Therefore, following the GDPR requirement for DIA may not only prevent but in essence eliminate a possibility of hearing an important social group who is capable of say. In some national cases of the YouCount a divide between ethics and data protection is very outspoken and a holistic consideration of the research project is missed. A dialogue must be set between the GDPR requirements and the epistemology of projects which rest on dialogical and participative communication and if the Open Science policy is to be implemented.
- The above recommendation, however, does not eliminate the necessity to secure certain formalities of project management such as clarifying roles, responsibilities, continuously tackling the increasing complexity of tasks for citizen scientists who do the work voluntarily. Therefore, trust rather than distrust to professional researchers' competence must be demonstrated;
- Special guidelines for research supervisory authorities and ethics committees are needed to enable continuation of CSS projects and ensure sustainability of the funding allocated for the YouCount and similar projects. A distinction between citizen natural sciences and social sciences must be more highlighted and facilitated to reduce tensions the YouCount teams has experienced.

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PARTNERS:

